

WATER AVAILABILITY AND IMPACTS OF LAND USE LAND COVER CHANGE IN MARSYANDGI RIVER BASIN, CENTRAL NEPAL

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By
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November, 2018

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work presented in this dissertation is a genuine work done originally by me and has not been submitted anywhere for the award of any degree. All the sources of information have been specifically acknowledged by reference to the author(s) or institution(s).

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ABSTRACT

The availability of freshwater has emerged as a serious concern in the globe. Land use land cover change (LULC) changes freshwater availability by disrupting surface water balance. In this study, the J2000 hydrological model is used to understand the effects of land use land cover change and its impact on the hydrological processes of the Marshyangdi river basin (MRB) (4074 km²) and one of its sub-catchments named Chepe Khola catchment (CKC) (307 km²). The model is able to represent hydrological processes of MRB and CKC with Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency, logarithm Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency and coefficient of determination with values 0.82, 0.87 and 0.82, 0.68, 0.83 and 0.68 respectively. The basin has the annual average precipitation of 1,985 mm/year, of which 20% is evapotranspiration, and its small catchment has annual precipitation of 2,454 mm/year, of which 22% is evapotranspiration. Three hypothetical scenarios were used to understand the impact of land use and land cover changes on hydrological processes of the MRB and CKC. In extreme scenario (scenario1) of forest clearance, overall discharge is increased by 1% in both, evapotranspiration is decreased by 2% in MRB and CKC, surface flow is increased by 10% in MRB but decreased by 12 % in CKC, interflow and base flow are decreased by 13% and by 11% in MRB but increased by 25% and 11% in CKC. In altitudinal swapping of cultivated land and forest (scenario 2), interflow and base flow is increased by 1% in MRB and by 4% and 6% respectively in CKC. Overland flow is increased in MRB but has a nominal change in CKC. This iterates that, the effect of LULC is distinctly observed in the hydrology of the small catchments and thus suggests for considering the smaller catchments in the policy level, developmental activities, and other similar studies. The results from the study can be used as decision support systems to inform policy formulation as the result is based on biophysical theories and well represent the basin and catchment dynamics.

Key Words: Water Balance, River Hydrology, Catchment Analysis, J2000 hydrological model, Himalaya region

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

°C	Degree Celsius
°F:	Degree Fahrenheit
AD	Amargosa Desert
CHAL	Chitwan Annapurna Landscape
CKC	Chepe Khola catchment
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DHM	Department of Hydrology and Meteorology
EASM	East Asian Summer Monsoon
ET	Evapotranspiration
GIS	Geographical Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRB	Gandaki River Basin
HI-AWARE	Himalayan Adaptation, Water and Resilience (HI-AWARE) Research on Glacier and Snowpack Dependent River Basins for Improving Livelihoods
HRU	Hydrological Response Units
ICIMOD	International Center for Integrated Mountain Development
J2k	J2000 Hydrological Model
KSL	Kailash Sacred Landscape in Nepal
LAI	Leaf Area Indices
LPS	Large Pore Storage
LULC	Land Use and Land Cover
masl	meter above sea level

MPS	Medium Pore Storage
MRB	Marsyangdi river Basin
OLI	Operational Land Imager
SE	South East
USGS	United States Geological Survey
WPI	Water Poverty Index

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Land use land cover (LULC) has become an issue of global concern because of its controls on food production, forest resources, regional and climate air quality, infectious disease, and availability in freshwater resources by disrupting the surface water balance, partitioning of precipitation into evapotranspiration, runoff, and groundwater flow (Foley et al., 2005). Changes in land use and cover lead to river flow redistribution, soil moisture and recharge fluctuations (He et al., 2008).

The significance of land use land cover change was highlighted in a project of the International Geosphere-Biosphere Program (IGBP), in 1987 and modeling is considered as an important aspect for the LULC study (Turner et al., 1994). Since then, the impacts of land use land cover change in hydrology have been studied in a different part of the world with different methods. Coupled models of land use land cover change and biophysical models are used as decision support systems for policy formulation (Veldkamp & Lambin, 2001).

Modeling the natural system of land use helps to improve understanding on dynamics of spatial and temporal land cover dynamics and helps for prediction and scenario generation in the context of the integrative assessment of global change (Brown et al., 2012). Modeling the land use land cover change is a powerful tool to assess the impact of land cover on biophysical processes, e.g. climate variability, land degradation, ecosystem stability and diversity (Veldkamp & Lambin, 2001).

Global-scale land use modeling is challenging and most land use change models are designed for local to regional scale studies (Meiyappan et al., 2014). Hydrological consequences of land use change are not easy to identify and quantify due to relatively short lengths of hydrological records, high natural variability of hydrological systems, difficulties in controlling land use change in real scenario, small number of the past experiments only in small-scale and challenges in generalizing results to other systems (DeFries & Eshleman, 2004).

Land cover change is one of the most important drivers of the ecosystem change and change in hydrological dynamics. The Hindu Kush Himalayan (HKH) region has

experienced severe forest degradation (Uddin et al., 2015). Losing forests increases flood potential, enhances drought impacts, and in another hand, an increase of forest cover in the basin, reduces wet season streamflow and raises streamflow in a dry season, thus reduce flood potentials in the wet season and also reduce drought severity in the dry season (Guo et al., 2008). In Nepal, a large number of areas of forests were degraded and lost due to the increasing demand for land and grown population (Reddy et al., 2018). Forested area has a higher rate of evapotranspiration and interception in comparison to grass and shrubland which influences the amount of water in streams and groundwater (Foley et al., 2005). The forests in the Lamjung district of Gandaki River Basin (GRB), have increased gradually in the last two decades with an overall decrease in shrub/grass and agriculture. At higher elevations, the forest area had increased at the cost of agricultural land and shrubland/grassland, while at lower elevations, the forest was more or less constant with an increase in agricultural land at the cost of shrub land/grassland (Bhawana, 2015).

As in other mid-hill districts, water availability in the Marsyangdi river basin (MRB) is a serious concern and water resource management in the river basin is emerging as an important issue. The assessment of the impact of land use land cover change in water availability and river discharge is important for the analysis of the water availability, hydropower development, development of irrigation system and development of water supply systems in the basin.

1.2 Rationale

Interaction of land use land cover change and hydrologic processes will be the major issue in the decades ahead (DeFries & Eshleman, 2004), as human actions are altering the terrestrial environment at unprecedented rates, magnitudes, and spatial scales. Global environmental change is the result of the land cover change, induced as a result of human land use practices (Turner et al., 1994) and water availability is influenced by the type of vegetation cover.

Hydrological modeling supports the study of vegetation response to climate variability, considering the factors that influence water availability and interactions between the atmosphere, the topography, the soil, as well as the vegetation (Teich et al., 2011). J2000 hydrological model is a physical, distributive modeling system, in which the topological HRU approach is used for catchment discretization (Krause, 2002). This model

implements the single processes in the hydrological cycle (ETP, snow, soil water, groundwater, lateral routing between the HRUs and channel routing) as encapsulated process modules, written in JAVA (Kralisch et al., 2005).

Along with hydropower (E.g. Upper Marsyangdi H.P., Middle-Marsyangdi H.P., Dordi Khola H.P., etc.), water from Marsyangdi river and its tributaries is being used for irrigating agricultural land. Some large irrigation systems e.g. Chepe Khola Nahar or Rainastar irrigation system, are operating, while some others are in the planning process. Almost a dozen hydropower projects are being constructed in the Marsyangdi river corridor along with many small and medium-sized projects in tributaries of the river (Karoobar, 2015). For long-term planning and management of water resources in the basin, current trend and future change in the pattern of water availability should be analyzed in advance (Shrestha & Dahal, 2016).

It is of keen importance to understand the different driving forces for LULC (Turner et al., 1994) and its impact on hydrology of the basin. Study on impacts of LULC and water availability help in providing the necessary input to decision making, that balance trade-off between the positive benefits of land-use change and potentially negative unintended consequences (DeFries & Eshleman, 2004). Land use land cover change brings changes in water availability and the impact is not well quantified in the case of this basin. Because of the small number of research and experiments, there is an absence of scientific information in full and there exists a partial understanding of the hydrological behavior of the basin. This makes the planner difficultly in decision making in regards to land use and water use.

1.3 Research Questions

This research is motivated by two major research questions:

- What are the hydrological dynamics of the Marsyangdi river basin and its smaller catchment- Chepe Khola?
- How does the land use land cover change impact the hydrological processes and water availability at a different scale of the basin?

1.4 Objectives

The major objective of the study is to understand the impacts of land use land cover change on hydrological dynamics of Marsyangdi river basin and its small catchment Chepe Khola

1.4.1 Specific Objectives

- To understand the hydrological dynamics of the Marsyangdi river basin (MRB)
- To explore catchment hydrology of Chepe Khola catchment
- To study the impact of land use land cover change in different scenarios in the Marsyangdi river basin and its catchment Chepe Khola

1.5 Scope and Limitations

This research covers the understanding of hydrological functioning of the Marshyangdi river basin and one of its catchment (Chepe Khola) in different LULC scenarios. The limitations of this study are:

- The high altitude region of the study area doesn't have input data for the whole study period.
- There is no precise geological information of the whole basin. Thus, the input file for geology consists of a single property, similar for the whole basin. Although the geological characteristics vary greatly within basin.
- The parameter file considers a few types (in this case, 4 types) of soil, after regrouping soil into different groups. The parameter value for the regrouped class may not represent exact soil property.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Land Use Land Cover

Globally, in the past 100 years, CO₂ emission to the atmosphere under influence of LUCC is 35% of total CO₂ emission from human activities, which is equivalent to the industrial era fossil fuel emissions to the atmosphere. This change has a direct impact on the global water-land-carbon cycle, the balance of energy, and a number of regional ecological balance (Chang et al., 2018). Perturbations in the surface energy balance generated by vegetation change from 2000 to 2015 have led to an average increase of 0.23 ± 0.03 °C in local surface temperature where the vegetation changes occurred (Duveiller et al., 2018).

The different models applied in the LULC study can broadly be categorized into mathematical equation-based, system dynamics, statistical, expert system, evolutionary, cellular, and hybrid. Multi-agent system models of land use land cover change (MAS/LUCC models) combines a cellular landscape model with agent-based representations of decision making, integrating the two components through the specification of interdependencies and feedbacks between agents and their environment (Parker et al., 2003). When the agricultural land use of Tocantins River, Southeastern Amazonia, increased from 30.2% in 1960 to 49.2% in 1995, with no significant change in precipitation, annual mean discharge increased by 24% ($P < 0.02$), the rainy season discharge increased by 28% ($P < 0.02$) and seasonal peaks occurred about one month earlier (Costa et al., 2003). Runoff is significantly (by 30%) decreased when tropical moist forest throughout the Amazon Basin and South East (SE) Asia has been replaced by scrub grassland in a version of the National Center for Atmospheric Research Community Climate Model (Version 1) (Henderson-Sellers et al., 1993). In the Brahmaputra basin, the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) was used to evaluate sensitivities and patterns in freshwater availability due to the projected climate and land use changes. In the basin, average annual Evapotranspiration (ET) was found to be sensitive to changes in CO₂ concentration and temperature, while total water yield, streamflow, and groundwater recharge were sensitive to changes in precipitation (Pervez & Henebry, 2015).

Point and areal studies investigating effects of LULC changes, have shown fluctuations in flow-direction of groundwater from upward (discharge) to downward (recharge),

when agricultural land is replaced with rangelands in the Amargosa Desert (AD) in Nevada and in the High Plains (HP) in Texas, US (Scanlon et al., 2005). An increase in rainy season discharge and mean discharge, with an earlier shift of seasonal peaks was observed in Tocantins River, Southeastern Amazonia when the forest is changed into agricultural land (Costa et al., 2003). In the Columbia river basin, long-term vegetation changes were evaluated and the evaluation indicated that the most important hydrological change has been a general tendency toward decreased vegetation maturity, and/or species conversion with the effect of generally reducing leaf area indices (LAI) (Matheussen et al., 2000).

In Nepal, national-level long-term datasets and studies of LULC are relatively scarce, except for those on a global scale (Paudel et al., 2016). National land cover database of Nepal, 2010 estimated that 39.1% of Nepal is covered by forests, 29.8% by agriculture, constituting patch and edges forest as 23.4% of national forest cover, revealing proximate biotic interferences over the forest. Satellite imaginary analysis has shown that the area of cropland in Nepal is increased by 13% over the past 50 years, urban land has increased rapidly over the past 32 years from 122 sq.km to 469 sq.km and snow covered area is reported to decrease (Paudel et al., 2016). Study using topographical prepared by U.S. Army Map Service, maps of Global Land Cover Facility (Landsat MSS), images of USGS (Landsat 8 OLI) and maps of Indian Remote Sensing satellite, have shown 76,710 sq.km of forests in 1930 has decreased to 39,392 sq.km in 2014, with net loss of 37,318 sq.km (48.6%) in Nepal (Reddy et al., 2018).

In Nepal, land use land cover change has been studied in a few local and watershed level. For instance, decadal land use changes in the Triyuga watershed has been assessed for the period between 1980 and 2015, in which the forest degradation (resulting in expansion of barren land) adversely affected the soil erosion leading to significant loss during the period between 1988 to 1997. The occurrence of disaster and the resulting losses can be compared with the changes in land use and precipitation in the Triyuga watershed (Choudhary & Pathak, 2016). Decrease in forest area by 9%, increase in cropland by 12%, decrease in large core forest by 10% were found using object-based image analysis of satellite images of Kailash Sacred Landscape in Nepal (KSL-Nepal) in land cover maps of 1992 and 2009, and 4% decline in forest cover, 10.6% decline in core forest, 5% increase in cropland was predicted by 2030, together with a slight increase in grassland and barren area accompanied by an increase in patch, perforated, small-sized

core, and medium-sized core areas (Uddin et al., 2015). Multi-temporal satellite imagery (Landsat Thematic Mapper, Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus, Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission Reflection, Radiometer images, and topographical maps) in combination with land use data and sociological information (semi-structured interviews and workshops) of Sagarmatha National Park revealed that the change in land cover differs according to altitudes. The snow and ice covered area is decreased with consequent expansion of glacial lakes and areas covered by rock and soil, above 6,000 masl, but forest and farmland are decreasing and areas for grazing, settlement, and shrubland are increasing, for the altitude between 3,000 and 6,000 masl (Garrard et al., 2016). The same study reported that anthropogenic activities are solely responsible in lower areas, though the impact of global climate change cannot be neglected as whole.

In Lamjung district of Marsyangdi river basin (MRB), study using geospatial information technologies and social research methods show decreasing number of households at high elevations (above 1400 m), where an increase in forest cover has been observed with a consequent decrease in agricultural land and shrubland/ grassland but at lower elevations (below 1400 m), forest cover has remained constant over the last 25 years, and the agricultural land area has increased but has become geometrically complex to meet the diverse needs and living requirements of the growing population (KC et al., 2017). In four watersheds of Tanahun and Kaski district in Chitwan Annapurna Landscape (CHAL), meteorological data, field-based soil properties (texture, bulk density and moisture content), LANDSAT images and DEM, topographic and base map from survey department, were used to understand relationship between water cycle and water budget in the watershed. In the watersheds, the higher the total vegetation cover, the less the amount of runoff (Thakur et al., 2017).

2.2 J2000 Hydrological Modelling

Jena Adaptable Modelling System (JAMS) is a Java open-source software framework that allows to build and apply environmental simulation models and have been successfully been applied to simulate hydrological, nutrient-transport and erosion processes around the world. J2000 model is a distributed and process-oriented hydrological model for hydrological simulations of mesoscale and macro-scale catchments. J2000 hydrological model was developed before Jena Adaptable Modelling System (JAMS) and the model provided the process core knowledge for JAMS (Krause & Kralisch, 2005). Some of the other popular J2000 models are Water and Nutrient

Balance Model (J2000-S), Hydrological Model J2000g, Inundation Model J2000-Flood and Gaussian Process Regression in JAMS framework. Implementation of J2000 into the Object Modelling System (OMS) has shown the suitability of the system for model development and application, and the combined model OMS/J2000 was a much faster comparison of OMS only (Kralisch et al., 2005).

The results produced by J2000 hydrological modeling shows a reasonably good fit for the sub-catchment analysis (Krause, 2002) and have offered the powerful tool to assess the impact of climate and landscape on water movement (Julian, 2018). In semi-arid conditions in the Western Cape, PRMS model and J2000 were able to match the timing of seasonal hydrograph responses, however, were not able to match annual discharge volumes and annual discharge was overestimated in certain cases and underestimated in others with daily Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiencies of below 0.4 (Bugan et al., 2009).

The J2000g model; simplified version of J2000, semi-distributed, rainfall-runoff model is used to estimate spatially distributed hydrological water balance components and demonstrated good validation performances, while the fully distributed J2000 model was more sensitive to data uncertainties (Krause & Kralisch, 2005). J2000g model with reduced calibration parameters, helped to understand limitations of traditional models and shows that traditional studies focusing only on one part of uncertainty; either the input uncertainty or the uncertainty arising from the choice of model structure and are limited in their explanatory power of the modeling performance, particularly in poorly gauged regions (Knoche et al., 2014).

J2000 hydrological model is being applied in different scenarios for different estimation. J2000 hydrological model simulated average groundwater recharge and hence, the safe yield estimation of natural groundwater in the Zarqa river catchment is in the same order of magnitude as estimated recharge rates obtained from analyzing stable isotope signatures and calculating chloride mass balance (Schulz et al., 2013). In a scenario from Germany, where agricultural land above 426 m was changed into the forested area, the spatial distribution of the mean runoff generation showed that, the southern part of the basin, which was the most affected region, generated significantly less runoff whereas, in the lower part, the runoff generation is more or less the same, despite some small patches where forests were changed to agriculture (Krause, 2002). J2000 model was applied in the Qugaqie (small (55 km²), Alpine (7.3 % of the total area is glacier covered)

catchment in central Tibetan Plateau (TP) with limited hydrological data to investigate on data, parameters and sensitivities have shown that the simulated discharge was generally less than the observed values and change in air temperature would cause a dramatic increase of discharge (Gao et al., 2012). Reconstruction of hydrological dynamics in Katulampa sub-basin, Indonesia was carried out by using the J2000 hydrological model and the hydrological dynamic during extreme events (i.e. high precipitation) was well represented (Julian, 2018).

J2000 model was used to understand the hydrological dynamics of a glaciated catchment; Dudh Koshi River basin in Nepal, and the hypothetical rise in temperature scenarios at a rate of +2 °C and +4 °C indicated that, snowmelt process might be largely affected with an increase in snowmelt volume is noted during the pre-monsoon period, whereas the contribution during the monsoon season is significantly decreased (Nepal et al., 2014). J2000 hydrological model efficiently captured hydrological behavior of Karnali river basin predicting the change in precipitation pattern with a further rise in temperature (Khatriwada & Nepal, 2016).

2.3 Marsyangdi River Basin

Marsyangdi river is in the Gandaki River Basin. The catchment area of GRB is 46,300 km²; 73% of the total area lies in Nepal (Bajracharya et al., 2011). The basin has significant importance for generation of hydropower in Nepal and with a huge concern of water availability.

In the hill region of GRB, the annual rainfall is an increasing trend, whereas the rainy days do not show any trend but in considering whole nation, there is a tendency toward later departure of monsoon, indicating an increase in its duration (Panthi et al., 2015). Meteorological and hydrological data from stations in GRB was mathematically modeled, graphed, plotted, analyzed and reported that increasing temperature and shifting rainfall patterns directly affect hydropower generation as most of the rivers in the Gandaki basin are snow and glacial feed rivers (Bajracharya et al., 2011).

In Gandaki River Basin, studies for quality and availability of water has been also studied. Analysis of the geochemical characteristics of river water in the glacier-fed semi-arid and humid subtropical segments of the GRB in Nepal reveal that the river has mostly retained its natural water quality but poses safety concern at a few locations and displayed the predominance of geogenic weathering processes in areas with carbonate dominant

lithology along with influence of climatic, and anthropogenic conditions (Pant et al., 2018). Water Poverty Index (WPI); targeting integrated assessment of physical availability of water resources, extent of access to water, water uses for different purposes, environmental factors impacting on ecology, water systems, and various capacities for sustaining access to water in Kali Gandaki river basin, is found to be 49.2, lower than the value at national level (WPI=54.4) indicating inappropriate water management plans rather than resource insufficiency (Manandhar et al., 2012).

In Marshyangdi river basin, HBV-6 model performance was adequate and able to simulate accurate result with estimated average discharge of 224.82 m³/s (1988-2009) and predicted decrease in rainy days while increase in frequency of intense rainfall, and the projected rainfall based on downscaling showed increase in rainfall for 2050's (Parajuli et al., 2016). Compared to the baseline period, the annual average of maximum temperature has been projected to increase by 0.82°C, 1.35°C and 2.29°C by 2090s, while, annual average of minimum temperature has been projected to increase by 0.87°C, 1.44°C and 2.43°C by 2090s and annual average precipitation has been projected to increase by 4, 14 and 21% by 2090s for RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 respectively (Khadka & Pathak, 2016). Along with the rise on temperature, in average, climate change is likely to increase water availability in the basin as suggested by the projected increase in average precipitation (Khadka & Pathak, 2016).

There exists a research gap in the analysis of water availability in the different scenario in the Marsyangdi river basin. In one hand, the change in land cover is being prevalent in the basin and in the another hand, the studies considering the whole Gandaki river basin may not represent the exact characteristics of the Marsyangdi river basin and the Chepe Khola catchment.

CHAPTER 3: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Area

Marsyangdi river basin is located between 27°56'7.9" N to 28°54'0.81" N latitudes, and 83°48'27.7" E to 84°41'50.6" E longitudes (figure 1). The basin has a total area of 4,074 sq. km. (Outlet station: Bimalnagar Station). Chepe Khola is one of the tributaries to the Marsyangdi river basin with area 307 sq.km. The Chepe Khola catchment lies in the Northern part of the basin which is characterized by the intense rainfall and also with higher evapotranspiration. This catchment does not have any glacial area, and the flow in the river is dominated by rainfall.

Figure 1 Study area

Marsyangdi river basin lies in the Gandaki River Basin (GRB). The GRB contains 3 of the world's 14 mountains peaks with the elevation over 8000 m; namely Dhaulagiri, Manaslu, and Annapurna. Marsyangdi river is one of the major tributaries of the Gandaki river along with Kali Gandaki, Seti Gandaki, Madi, Daraudi, Budhi Gandaki, and Trishuli. Geologically, the basin extends from High Himalaya in the north to the Lesser Himalayan region in the south (Khadka & Pathak, 2016). Marsyangdi river basin lies in Gandaki province, in Lamjung, Manang, Gorkha, and Tanahun districts and there are 25

municipalities (rural and urban) in the basin. The river is a hub for many hydropower plants in caskets.

3.2 Framework of Study

The spatial-temporal data of land cover, soil, geography, geology etc. required for the model were collected and prepared. The model JAMS/J2000(version 3.9) was downloaded from the University of Jena (<http://jams.uni-jena.de/>). The model is based on the Hydrological Response Unit (HRU) which is prepared by the online tool HRUweb, available in the university web platform (<http://intecral.uni-jena.de/hruweb-qs/>). The model then set up in the basin, calibrated, validated and further analysis was done. Data sources and details are explained in section 3.7. The data obtained are analyzed to get the results. The framework of this study is represented in figure 2.

Figure 2 Framework of the study

3.3 J2000 Hydrological Model

The J2000 hydrological model was downloaded from the website of the University of Jena (<http://jams.uni-jena.de/downloads/>). In the J2000 model, simulation of different hydrological processes is carried out in encapsulated process modules (figure 3) which are to a great extent independent of each other. This allows changing, substituting or adding single modules or processes without restructuring the model once again from the initial.

Figure 3: Principal layout of J2000 hydrological model, Krause (2001) and Nepal et al. (2014)

3.4 Modules within the J2000 Hydrological Model

3.4.1 Precipitation Distribution Module

In the J2000 modeling system, precipitation firstly is distributed between rain and snow depending upon the air temperature. Two calibration parameters (Trns, and Trs) are used where ‘Trs’ is base temperature and Trns is a temperature range (upper and lower boundary) above and below the base temperature. It is assumed that precipitation below a certain threshold temperature results in total snow precipitation and exceeding second threshold results in total rainfall as precipitation to determine the amount of rain and snow.

3.4.2 Interception Module

This module calculates of net precipitation from the field precipitation against the particular vegetation covers and their development in the annual variation. Net precipitation only occurs when the maximum interception storage capacity of the vegetation is exhausted. The surplus is then passed on through falling precipitation to the following module.

$$Int_{max} = \alpha \cdot LAI [mm]$$

Where Int_{max} is maximum interception capacity, α is storage capacity per m^2 leaf area against the precipitation type [mm], LAI is the leaf area index of the particular land use class taken from the land use parameter file.

3.4.3 Snow Module

The snow development is sub-divided into 3 phases in snow module: the snow accumulation, the metamorphosis, and the snowmelt. The amount of snow of the total precipitation is defined via air temperature in order to calculate the daily accumulation rate. For this purpose, it is assumed that going below a particular threshold temperature, the total precipitation consists of snow and for going above a second threshold temperature, the total precipitation consists of rain. In the zone between these threshold temperatures, mixed precipitation occurs. In order to define the threshold temperatures and therefore the size of the transition zone, a temperature value (Trs in $^{\circ}C$) needs to be given which conforms to the temperature, where 50% of precipitation is snow and 50% is rain.

$$potMR = t_factor.T + r_factor.P + g_factor[mm]$$

Where potMR is potential melting rate, r_factor, g_factor, and t_factor are generated empirically in the model, T is temperature ($^{\circ}C$), P is Precipitation (mm)

3.4.4 Glacier Module

This module is integrated as a separate module into the standard J2000 hydrological model, as a part of the study in the Koshi river basin (Nepal, 2012). This module estimates snow and ice- melt (SIM) runoff and the output is directly provided to a stream as overland flow (RD1).

Unique land use ID was provided for glacier area as a GIS layer during HRU delineation and thus, all processes which occur in the glacier were separately treated based on this unique ID. First, seasonal snow occurs on top of the glacier (or glacier HRU) and produces snow runoff. Ice melts in two conditions to produce the runoff. In the first condition, ice melts, if the entire snow cover of glacier HRU is melt and in the second condition, the ice melt, if meltTemp crosses the base temperature.

3.4.4 Soil Water Module

The soil module is structured in process units (infiltration, evapotranspiration) and store units (middle pore storage, large pore storage, and depression storage). At first, the infiltration capacity against water saturation in soil and a maximum infiltration rate is estimated with the help of an empirical method. The maximum infiltration rate functions as a threshold. When this threshold is crossed, the surplus water is stored in depression storage or lead to direct surface runoff. The maximum amount of water that can be held back in surface depressions is seen as maximum depression storage (maxDepStor). Furthermore, the depression storage is dependent on the surface structure as well as on slope and is halved when the slope is greater than 5%. The water (from precipitation) that is not infiltrated or stored in the depression storage drains as surface runoff. In order to calculate the infiltration (Inf), an empirical calculation method is used.

3.4.5 Ground Water Module

The modeling concept of groundwater module is for viewing the groundwater runoff of all geologic formations that occur in the catchment area in consideration of different storage and runoff behaviors. In individual geologic units, there is a distinction between the upper ground-water reservoir (RG1) in loose weathered material with high permeability and the lower ground-water reservoir (RG2) in fractures and clefts of the bedrock. Consequently, two runoff components are generated: a fast one from the upper ground-water reservoir and a slow one from the lower ground-water reservoir. The filling of the ground-water reservoir results from the vertical runoff component of the soil module. The emptying can be carried out by the lateral subterranean runoff components as well as capillary elevation in the unsaturated zone.

3.4.6 Lateral Routing Module

The lateral routing module describes the transfer of water within a flow cascade from HRU to HRU from the upper catchment area until the receiving stream. Since the retention mechanisms of the runoff are described by the other process modules, here only the HRU's influxes and discharges are allocated. The water transfer between the HRUs is seen as n:1 relation. Thus, an HRU can have several influxes but only one discharge. The order of the HRUs as receivers is determined by the topologic ID of the HRU dataset. In the HRU dataset, it is also determined which HRUs finally drain in the receiving stream.

3.4.7 Reach Routing Module

The reach routing module describes the flow phenomena in the channel via a cinematic wave-like normal mode and the calculation of the rapidity of flow according to MANNING and STRICKLER. There is only one parameter called the routing coefficient (TA), that needs to be set by the user. It represents the travel time of the discharge wave which moves from the channel to the runoff after a precipitation event. Its value, as well as the stream's rapidity of flow and the flow length, is needed for the calculation of a runoff retention coefficient.

The higher the assumed value of TA, the faster the discharge wave moves within a particular period and the less water remains in the channel. The theoretical value range, therefore corresponds to one of the positive numbers.

3.5 Regionalization of Data and Specific Corrections

The regionalization of data in the J2000 hydrological model is done in two steps. Firstly, the data undergoes general processing and secondly, specific correction and calculation are performed. General processing is carried out by four different methods. The methods could be 'Linear regression between daily values and elevation of stations', 'defining gauging stations near particular HRU', 'Inverse-Distance-Weighted(IDW)' and 'calculation of values for each HRUs'.

For the individual datasets, specific correction and calculation methods are applied. Corrections are performed for moistening error, evaporation error, wind error and specific calculations are performed for relative humidity, sunshine duration, wind speed, temperature, net radiation balance, and evapotranspiration. The correction and calculation are performed by the model as described in the web portal of the model (http://jams.uni-jena.de/ilmswiki/index.php/Hydrological_Model_J2000#Regionalization_of_Climate_and_Precipitation_Data).

3.6 Hydro-meteorological Input Data

The J2000 hydrological model requires hydrological and meteorological data (precipitation, humidity, wind, sunshine hour, temperature and runoff) as input data for the model initialization. Detail description of the input data is described in Appendix 1.

There are two hydrological stations (table 1) and six meteorological stations (table 2) in the Marsyangdi river basin (figure 4). Since, the wind data and sunshine hour data are not available from stations inside the basin, Gorkha station and Pokhara airport station, even being out of basin (figure 4), are used for wind and sunshine hour respectively (table 2).

Table 1 Hydrological stations in Marsyangdi river basin

S.N.	Hydrological Parameter	No. of Station	Stations(Station ID)
1	Discharge in Marsyangdi river basin	1	Bimalnagar (439)
2	Discharge in Chepe Khola catchment	1	Garambesi (440)

Table 2 Meteorological stations in Marsyangdi river basin

S.N.	Meteorological Parameters	No. of Stations	Stations (Station ID)
1	Humidity	2	Khudi Bazar (802), Chame (816)
2	Precipitation	6	KhudiBazar (802), Kunchha (807), Chame (816), ManagBhot (820), GhareDhunga (823), PhuGaun (834)
3	Sunshine Hours	1	Pokhara Airport (804)
4	Temperature	2	Khudi Bazar (802), Chame (816)
5	Wind Speed	1	Gorkha (809)

Figure 4 Digital Elevation Model and DHM stations in the Marsyangdi river basin

The meteorological and hydrological input data for the basin were obtained from the Department of Hydrology and Meteorology (DHM), Government of Nepal. Daily precipitation, daily discharge, daily temperature (minimum and maximum), daily wind, daily humidity was obtained from 1987 to 2015. Missing data of precipitation and discharge was replaced by the value -9999 but missing data of other parameters (precipitation, temperature, and humidity) are filled by the value obtained by average of 6 records (of same day of past 3 years and same day of 3 years ahead) for each missing value of the day.

3.7 Model Parameter Files and Input Data

The J2000 hydrological model requires the following temporal static parameter files for the model initialization:

- soils.par – soil parameter file
- landuse.par – landuse parameter file
- hgeo.par – hydrogeology parameter file
- hrus.par – parameter of the derived Hydrological Response Units (HRUs)
- reach.par – reach parameter file

3.7.1 Soil Parameter File

The soil parameter data of the study river basin was downloaded from Soil and Terrain database for Nepal (version 1.0), at scale of 1:1 million (SOTER_Nepal; <http://data.isric.org/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/896e61f8-811a-40f9-a859-ee3b6b069733>). SOTER_Nepal is generalized database from the original Soils and Terrain database of Nepal at scale 1:50,000 compiled by FAO and Survey Department of Nepal. The SOTER_Nepal database provides generalized information on landform and soil properties at a scale of 1:1 million. It consists of 17 SOTER units, characterized by 56 representatives and four synthetic profiles for which there are no measured soil data. The SOTER database includes also attribute data of 99 profiles initially selected as references to soil components that already have a representative profiles. From the soil file, comprehensive information on water holding capacity, textural information at different horizons were also extracted. In the reclassified map, Cambisols includes Humic Cambisols(CMu), Eutric Cambisols(CMe),: Chromic Cambisols(CMx), Gleyic Cambisols(CMg) (figure 5).

Figure 5 Reclassified soil types in the Marsyangdi river basin

3.7.2 Land Cover Parameter File

The land use parameter file requires information about the land use and land cover of a catchment that controls the different aspects of hydrology. J2000 requires the major

classification of LULC which affect hydrological dynamics and parameter values are either taken from literature review or from remote sensing data. The description of the considered parameters is presented in Appendix 3.

The land use land cover data was downloaded from the website of GlobCover (http://due.esrin.esa.int/page_globcover.php) of the European Space Agency (ESA). The land cover map is derived by automatic and regionally-tuned classification of a time series of global MERIS FR mosaics for the year 2009. The global land cover map counts 22 land cover classes defined with the United Nations (UN) Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) (Sophie et al., 2010).

Glacier Data

The data was downloaded from the website of International Central for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD) (rds.icimod.org). This dataset is created using Landsat TM, ETM+ imageries of 2010. The glacier outlines were derived semi-automatically using object-based image classification (OBIC) method, separately for clean ice and debris cover and further editing and validation was done carefully by draping over the high-resolution images from Google Earth (ICIMOD, 2014). The glaciers data obtained from “ICIMOD glacier inventory, 2010” was overlaid using the mosaic function of ArcMap software and reclassified in nine different classes (figure 6).

Figure 6 Land cover in Marsyangdi river basin

3.7.3 Hydro-geological Parameter File

In the absence of suitable datasets to represent geological characteristics of all parts of MRB, single geological characteristic is considered for the whole basin. The value of RG1, RG2, RG1_K, and RG2_k in this parameter is imagined the same for the whole basin.

The storage capacity of the upper (RG1) and lower (RG2) groundwater storage can be estimated by analyzing geological information of the area. The storage capacity is normally controlled by the geological formation, rock types, origin and nature of rocks and permeability. These values are expressed as maximum storage volume in mm/day of each storage type. The storage coefficient values (RG1_k and RG2_k) are used as a general recession co-efficient of two storages. These are expressed as a retention time in days in the particular storage. The recession is further controlled by a flexible calibration parameter within the model. Appendix 5 enlists the parameters under hydrogeology.

3.7.4. Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

A digital elevation model is a bare-earth raster grid referenced to a vertical datum. The Digital Elevation model was downloaded from the web portal of USGS (earthexplorer.usgs/). The resolution was changed into 250*250 and projected in UTM to feed in the model system in ArcMap 10.3. The output of DEM is shown in Figure 8.

3.7.5 HRUs and Reach Parameter Files

HRUs are spatial model entities that are distributed, heterogeneous structured entities having a common climate, land use, soil, and geology controlling their hydrological dynamics (Fischer et al., 2009). The areas which comprise similar properties such as topography (slope, aspects), land use, soil and geology, and behave similarly in their hydrological response, are merged to develop an HRU. The web portal of Jena University (<http://intecral.uni-jena.de/hruweb-qs/>) is used for delineating HRUs and reaches which demanded the input of the files such as, Digital Elevation Model (DEM), soil, land use, and Hydro-geology raster files and the discharge/output point of the area. Parameter values used for the production of HRU illustrated in Appendix 6.

The reach parameter file store information about stream characteristics as well as the relationship between stream networks to accomplish reach routing. The reach parameter file contains information on the structure of the flow topology by noting the ID for every reach into which it transfers. The reach parameter is produced along with the HRU

delineation process. Details datasets used for the Marsyangdi river basin are shown in Appendix 7. In the Marsyangdi river basin 3,715 HRUs are formed and in Chepe Khola catchment 285 HRUs are formed (figure 7).

Figure 7 Hydrological Response Units (HRUs)

3.8 Modelling Strategies

3.8.1 Calibration and Validation of the Model

The model was calibrated and validated using the split sample method (Klemeš, 1986). Manual ‘hit and trial method’ was applied for adjusting parameter values in the calibration period, with reference to global average provided in model and values used in the Dudhkoshi river basin. The calibration parameters with the range and values are listed in Appendix 7.

3.8.2 Evaluation of Model Performance

The quality of parameter sets in model outcome to represent real scenario is quantified by error metrics like the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency, coefficient of determination, and index of agreement (Fischer et al., 2009) and these efficiencies are frequently used in hydrologic modeling studies (Krause et al., 2005). The efficiencies for providing information on a systematic and dynamic way during model simulation are as follows:

Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (E):

The efficiency E proposed by Nash and Sutcliffe in 1970, is defined as one minus the sum of the absolute squared differences between the predicted and observed values normalized by the variance of the observed values during the period under investigation.

$$E = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (Q_m^t - Q_o^t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T (Q_o^t - \bar{Q}_o)^2}$$

Where, \bar{Q}_o is the mean of observed discharges, and Q_m is modeled discharge. Q_o^t is observed discharge at time t. E can range from $-\infty$ to 1.

Coefficient of Determination (r^2):

The coefficient of determination (r^2) is defined as the squared value of the coefficient of correlation according to Bravais-Pearson. It is calculated as

$$r^2 = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - \bar{O}) (P_i - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{o})^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2}} \right)^2$$

Where, O is observed and P is predicted values. The range of r^2 lies between 0 and 1 which describes how much of the observed dispersion is explained by the prediction. A value of zero means no correlation at all, whereas a value of 1 means that the dispersion of the prediction is equal to that of the observation.

Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency with Logarithmic Values (lnE):

The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency E is calculated with logarithmic values of O and P to reduce the problem of the squared differences and the resulting sensitivity to extreme values. Through this logarithmic transformation, runoff values of the peaks are flattened and the low flows is increased in comparison to flood peaks resulting in an increase in sensitivity of lnE to systematic model over or under prediction.

P-BIAS:

P-BIAS is deviation of the simulation from the observed data, expressed as a percentage. The optimal value of P-BIAS is 0 with low-magnitude values indicating accurate model simulation. Positive values indicate model underestimation bias, and negative values indicate model overestimation bias. It is calculated as

$$PBIAS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q_i^{obs} - Q_i^{sim})}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i^{obs}} \times 100$$

Where, Q_i^{obs} is the i^{th} observation for the daily flow, Q_i^{sim} is the i^{th} simulation value for the daily flow, mean is the mean of observed data for the daily flow, and n is the total number of daily flow observations.

3.9 Hydrological Analysis of the Basin

Water balance, runoff, rainfall, and evapotranspiration are analyzed in a yearly and monthly basis for the basin and in the catchment.

3.10 Land Use Land Cover Scenarios

Three hypothetical scenarios are considered in this study. The scenarios are as follows:

3.10.1 Scenario 1: All forest is converted into the barren land

In this hypothetical scenario, all types of forest in the basin are changed into barren land. Two parameters inside the model; SoilImpGT80 and SoilImpLT80, are adjusted for adjusting the infiltration in this scenario.

3.10.2 Scenario 2: Change in agricultural land

In this scenario, cropland and shrub-land above 1,500 masl is changed into forest and forested land and shrub land below 1,500 masl is converted into cropland. This scenario is set to understand recent land use change in the area, the imaginative scenario is based on the study which reported that the mountain areas there was agriculture land contract (by about 2200 ha) and in plains agriculture expansion (by about 2100 ha) (Chitale & Maharjan, 2017). The reality is exaggerated to develop a scenario to extreme level.

3.10.3 Scenario 3: Change in the glaciated area

This scenario imagines that the current glacier-covered area is shifted above by 1,500 masl. Currently, the glacier-covered area exists from 3,928 masl. In this scenario, all glacier-covered area below 5,428 masl is converted into bare land. Snow covered area is decreased in recent decades in Nepal (Paudel et al., 2016) and is projected to be decreasing further.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

4.1 Hydrological Dynamics of Marsyangdi River Basin

J2000 hydrological model provided essential data/results to analyze water balance, precipitation trend, evapotranspiration, discharge and runoff components in the river.

4.1.1 Calibration and Validation

The overall characteristics of the river basin are well captured by the J2000 hydrological model. Visually, the discharge recorded from the observed station and the discharge calculated through the model is similar. The calibration was done for 8 years from 2002 to 2009 (figure 8) and validation was done for 5 years from 2011 to 2015 (figure 9). The efficiencies are discussed further.

Figure 8 Observed and simulated runoff in the Marsyangdi river basin for the calibration period; 2002-2009

Figure 9 Observed and simulated runoff in Marsyangdi river basin for validation period; 2011-2015

The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency (E), Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency with logarithm (LnE) and coefficient of determination (r^2) for the calibration period is 0.82, 0.83 and 0.82 respectively, while for the validation period the values are 0.77, 0.86 and 0.82 respectively. Likewise, during the whole period of 1987-2015, the efficiencies are: 0.82, 0.87 and 0.82 respectively (table 3). The volume bias for calibration, validation and overall period are -4.13, -19.78 and -4.56 respectively (table 3).

Table 3 Efficiency of the model in the Marsyangdi river basin

	Calibration	Validation	Overall
Timeframe	2002-2009	2011-2015	1987-2015
Nash-Sutcliffe (E)	0.82	0.77	0.82
Nash-Sutcliffe with logarithm (LnE)	0.83	0.86	0.87
Coefficient of determination (r^2)	0.82	0.82	0.82
Volume bias (p-bias)	-4.13	-19.78	-4.56

The model has captured the flow of all the seasons. The average observed and simulated discharge of Marsyangdi river basin at Bimalnagar station is 217 m³/Sec and 208 m³/Sec

respectively, for the whole study period (1987-2015). The model overestimated the discharge for the months of March, April, May, and June but underestimated in July, August, September, October and November (figure 10).

Figure 10 Observed and simulated runoff of the Marsyangdi river basin for the overall model running period; 1987-2015

4.1.2 Water Balance

Marsyangdi river is a glacial fed river in which precipitation contributes most to river discharge. The analysis of water balance components for 29 years (1987 to 2015) has shown that Marsyangdi river basin receives total annual average precipitation of 1,985 mm; 80% as rainfall and 20 % as snowfall. Most of the water (i.e.75%) received by the river basin goes out of basin as river discharge, about 20 % leaves basin in the form of evapotranspiration and about 5% is stored in different forms (figure 11) like snow storage, glacial storage, soil pore storage, deep percolation storage etc. The basin received maximum rainfall (2,688mm) in 1999 and minimum rainfall (1669 mm) in 1992 and in 1988 and 1998 the storage was negative (table 4).

Table 4 Water balance components (1987-2015)

Year	Input (mm)	Evapotranspiration (mm)	Discharge (mm)	Storage (mm)
1987	2,284	409	1,719	157
1988	2,567	439	2,153	-25
1989	2,210	439	1,682	90
1990	2,186	378	1,717	91
1991	2,044	353	1,588	103
1992	1,669	486	1,182	2
1993	2,087	461	1,621	5
1994	2,060	444	1,558	58
1995	2,449	445	1,770	234
1996	2,400	422	1,843	135
1997	2,164	269	1,546	350
1998	2,342	371	2,059	-88
1999	2,688	424	2,063	201
2000	2,132	410	1,641	81
2001	1,947	422	1,433	92
2002	2,177	394	1,648	135
2003	2,171	397	1,684	90
2004	2,159	415	1,658	86
2005	1,841	435	1,321	85
2006	1,837	437	1,366	34
2007	2,350	420	1,730	200
2008	2,261	415	1,695	150
2009	2,256	444	1,469	342
2010	2,064	451	1,588	25
2011	2,010	420	1,515	76
2012	2,047	446	1,527	74
2013	1,914	499	1,214	200
2014	2,345	413	1,568	364
2015	1,792	438	1,263	92
Average	2,154	421	1,614	119
Percentage	100	20	75	5

Figure 11 Water balance in the Marsyangdi river basin (1987-2015)

4.1.3 Precipitation

The basin receives precipitation in the form of rainfall and snowfall. The average total annual precipitation is 1,985 mm, the average annual rainfall is 1,597 mm and the average snowfall is 385 mm. Total precipitation is higher in 4 months of the monsoon period. The average total precipitation is lower in high altitude areas of Manag district but higher in the areas between the elevation range of 1,000-1,200 masl. The overall precipitation and rainfall are in a decreasing trend from 1987 to 2015 but the snowfall is observed to have an increasing trend (figure 12).

Figure 12 Annual precipitation in the Marsyangdi river basin

4.1.4 Evapotranspiration

About 20% (~19.53%) of the average total precipitation in the basin is evaporated between 1987 to 2015. The total average potential and actual evapotranspiration are 433 mm/year and 421 mm/year respectively. The highest actual evapotranspiration occurs in the month of May (54 mm) and lowest in January (18 mm)(figure 13).

Figure 13 Total monthly average potential and actual evapotranspiration in MRB

The actual evapotranspiration is in a range of 0.0-0.06 mm/day in higher elevation and is in range of 3.1 – 5.5 mm/day in lower elevation (figure 14).

Figure 14 Average daily actual evapotranspiration in the Marsyangdi river basin

4.1.5 Runoff Components

J2000 facilitates analysis of runoff diving into four different components. In the Marsyangdi river basin, overland flow (RD1) contributes 59%, interflow 1 (RD2) contributes 17%, interflow 2 (RG1) contributes 14% and Base flow (RG2) contributes 10% in total flow (runoff). The overland flow contributes 73% (maximum) in July (monsoon period) and 6% in January(winter), the interflow contributes 22%(maximum) in April and May, whereas the base flow contributes 44% in January and contribution of components varies in a different season (figure 15).

Figure 15 Runoff components in the Marsyangdi river basin

4.1.6 Snow and Glacial Contribution

The total flow in the river is contributed by rain, glacial melt, ice melt, spring water, and groundwater. The river discharge in an average, receive 169 mm/year from ice and snow melt. In average, glacier runoff (snowmelt over the glacier, ice runoff, and rain runoff) contributes 16 % of total flow, the snow melt from non-glaciated area contributes 14% of total flow. The snow melt only from the glacial area contributes 5 % of total flow. Glacier runoff contributes 27% (maximum) in April and 3% (minimum) whereas non-glacier runoff contributes 45% (maximum) in March and 7% (minimum) in November and December (figure 16). Total glacier and non-glacier runoff contribute 69% (maximum) but 13%(minimum) in December.

Figure 16 Glacier and snowmelt contribution in the runoff in MRB

4.2 Catchment Hydrology of Chepe Khola

4.2.1 Calibration and Validation

The model is able to represent the catchment hydrology. Like in the Marsyangdi river basin, the study period for Chepe Khola catchment is 1987 – 2015. The model was calibrated for 8 years from 2002 to 2009 (figure 17) and validated for 5 years from 2011 to 2015 (figure 18).

Figure 17 Observed and simulated runoff in Chepe Khola catchment for the calibration period; 2002- 2009

Figure 18 Observed and simulated runoff in Chepe Khola catchment for the validation period; 2011-2015

The Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency, Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency with logarithm and Coefficient of determination are 0.60, 0.78 and 0.62 in calibration period, 0.68, 0.83 and 0.69 in validation period and 0.68, 0.83 and 0.68 in overall running period respectively. The volume bias is calculated as 1.93, -10.96 and -4.51 in calibration, validation and in overall period respectively (table 5).

Table 5 Efficiency of Model in Chepe Khola catchment

	Calibration	Validation	Overall
Timeframe	2002-2009	2011-2015	1987-2015
Nash-Sutcliffe (E)	0.60	0.68	0.68
Nashi-Sutcliffe Logarithm (LnE)	0.78	0.83	0.83
Coefficient of Determination (r^2)	0.62	0.69	0.68
Volume Bias (P-bias)	1.93	-10.96	-4.51

The observed average annual runoff in Garambesi station is 24.93 m³/Sec and the simulated average runoff is 24.25 m³/sec. The runoff is under-estimated in the months from August to January and overestimated in other months (figure 19).

Figure 19 Observed and simulated runoff of Chepe Khola catchment for the whole study period; 1987-2015

4.2.2 Water Balance

In average, from 1987 to 2015, the Chepe Khola catchment receives total precipitation of 3,207 mm/year. All most all (i.e. 99%) of total precipitation occurs as rainfall and very less (i.e.1 %) occurs as snowfall. Out of total precipitation (input), about 78 % of input flows out as discharge, about 22 % is evaporated and very less (i.e.0.01%) is stored in different forms. Out of 29 years, 15 different years have a negative value for storage (table 6).

Table 6 Water balance in Chepe Khola catchment

Year	Input (mm)	Evapotranspiration (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Storage (mm)
1987	3,399	791	2,516	92
1988	3,499	791	2,709	0
1989	3,082	780	2,321	-19
1990	3,345	594	2,674	76
1991	3,019	544	2,522	-47
1992	2,412	908	1,573	-69
1993	3,156	759	2,357	41
1994	2,985	761	2,308	-83
1995	3,619	788	2,699	132
1996	3,469	727	2,797	-54
1997	2,652	449	2,016	187
1998	3,475	573	3,026	-125
1999	3,695	700	3,034	-39
2000	3,455	704	2,783	-32
2001	3,403	721	2,656	26
2002	3,447	656	2,758	34
2003	3,607	652	2,996	-41
2004	3,429	672	2,707	51
2005	2,997	732	2,271	-5
2006	3,098	656	2,507	-65
2007	3,454	674	2,746	34
2008	3,817	696	3,133	-13
2009	2,530	743	1,844	-57
2010	3,307	782	2,492	34
2011	3,082	733	2,335	14
2012	3,201	817	2,466	-82
2013	2,524	772	1,700	51
2014	3,394	765	2,538	91
2015	2,459	837	1,738	-116
Average	3,207	716	2,490	0.46
Percentage	100	22	77.09	0.01

4.2.3 Evapotranspiration

Out of total input, about 22% in an average evaporates from the Chepe Khola catchment. The yearly total average potential and actual evapotranspiration are 719 mm and 716 mm respectively. The actual evapotranspiration in May is 98 mm(highest) and on December 28 mm(lowest). In April, May, Jun the potential evapotranspiration is 97.2 mm, 100.1 mm and 80.4 mm and the actual evapotranspiration is 96.8 mm, 98.6 mm and 79.4 mm respectively (figure 20).

Figure 20 Average monthly evapotranspiration in CKC

4.2.3 Runoff

The overland flow contributes about 60% of the total flow, the interflow 1 contributes 10%, interflow 2 contributes 17% and base flow contributes 13% of the total flow in the catchment. Overland flow is 478 mm(maximum) in August and 0.62 mm(minimum) in November, Interflow 1 is 69 mm(maximum) in August and 0.5 mm(minimum) in February, interflow 2 is 60 mm(maximum) in August and 15mm in April(minimum) and base flow is 38 mm(maximum) in September and 20 mm(minimum) in April (figure 21).

Figure 21 Runoff components in CKC

4.3 Impact of Land Use Land Cover Change in Different Scenarios

Three different scenarios are imagined including the extreme scenario of forest clearance, an altitudinal shift of cropland and change in a glacial covered area as described in section 3.10. In scenario 1 and Scenario 2, the area of 5 (out of 9) types of land cover are changed. In scenario 1, all three types of forest are converted to bare land, hence the percentage of these is 0 and in scenario 2, there is swapping of forest and agricultural land (table 8 and table 9).

Table 7 Change in the area in the Marsyangdi river basin at different scenarios

Description	Area in percentage		
	Baseline	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Cropland/Vegetation	23	23	16
Broadleaved Forest	6	0	4
Needle-leaved Forest	15	0	14
Mixed Forest	4	0	14
Bare Areas	19	44	19

Table 8 Change in the area in Chepe Khola catchment at different scenarios

Description	Area in percentage		
	Baseline	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Cropland/Vegetation	39	39	43
Broadleaved Forest	23	0	17
Needle leaved Forest	14	0	13
Mixed Forest	11	0	14
Bare Areas	0	48	0

4.3.1 Impacts of Scenario 1 and Scenario 2

Evapotranspiration

In the Marsyangdi river basin, average yearly evapotranspiration decreases by 2% and 4% than baseline in scenario 1 i.e. clearance of forest, and scenario 2 i.e. change in agricultural land, respectively. In scenario 1, the evapotranspiration increases in January by 1%, July by 5%, August by 5%, September by 3% and October by 2% but decrease in March by 7%, April by 12%, May by 9%, June by 3%, November by 4% and December by 3% (figure 22). In scenario 2, the evapotranspiration is decreased in all months in comparison with baseline (figure 22).

Figure 22 Evapotranspiration on different scenarios in MRB

In Chepe Khola catchment, average annual evapotranspiration is decreased by 2% and 6% in scenario 1 and scenario 2 respectively. In scenario 1, the evapotranspiration increased in January by 3%, February by 1%, July by 8%, August by 5%, September by 2%, October by 2% and December by 2% but decreased in March by 6%, April by 11%, May by 4% and in November by 1% (figure 23). In scenario 2, the evapotranspiration is decreased in all months in comparison with baseline (figure 23).

Figure 23 Evapotranspiration on the different scenario in CKC

Discharge and Runoff Components

The average yearly discharge of the Marsyangdi river basin in Bimalnagar station is increased by 1% in both scenarios. In scenario 1, the overall discharge is decreased in October by 2%, November by 7%, December by 8% and January by 4% but increased in March by 3%, April by 7% and May by 10% and constant in other months. In scenario 2, discharge is increased in all months.

Figure 24 Overland flow in different scenarios in MRB

In MRB, overland flow is increased by 10% and 1 % in scenario 1 and scenario 2, respectively. In scenario 1, the overland flow in February is 2.6 times of baseline, but in

August the overland flow is same of bassline and in scenario 2, overland flow is almost similar throughout all months (figure 24).

Figure 25 Interflow in different scenarios in MRB

Interflow is decreased by 13% and increased by 1% in scenario 1 and scenario 2 respectively. In scenario 1, interflow is decreased by 24% in April and by 9% in July and August but in scenario 2, the interflow is consistently increased by about 1% in all months (figure 25).

Figure 26 Base flow in the different scenario in MRB

Base flow is decreased by 11 % in scenario 1 and increased by 3 % in scenario 2. In Scenario 1, baseflow is decreased by 12% in December and by 10% in September but in scenario 2, baseflow is increased by 3% in June, July, August and September and by about 2% in all other months (figure 26).

The average discharge in Chepe Khola catchment, at Garambesi station, has been increased by 1% in scenario 1 and by 2% in scenario 2. In scenario 1, the discharge has been decreased by 5% in July and by 4% in August but increased by 16% in April. In scenario 2, runoff is increased in all months but decreased by 0.2% in August.

Figure 27 Overland flow in the different scenario in CKC

In CKC, the overland flow has been decreased by 12% in scenario 1 and decreased by nominal in scenario 2. In scenario 1, overland flow is increased by 49% in January, by 93% in February, by 74% in March, by 56% in April, by 7% in May by 76% in November and by 30% in December and decreased by 7% in June, by 14% in July, by 14% in August, by 13% in September and by 7% in October (figure 27). In scenario 2, overland flow is increased by 3% in March, 10% in April, by 7% in May and by 3% in June.

Figure 28 Interflow in different scenarios in CKC

Total interflow (interflow 1+interflow 2) has been increased by 24% in scenario 1 and by 4 % in scenario 2. Monthly interflow is increased by 36% in July and 12% in April in scenario1 but increased by 1% in July and by 7% in November (figure 28).

Figure 29 Base flow in different scenarios at CKC

Base flow is increased by 10% and 6% in scenario 1 and scenario 2 respectively. In scenario 1, base flow is increased by 13% in August and by 7% in November but in scenario 2, base flow is increased by 8% in July and August and by 4% in November (figure 29).

4.3.2 Impacts of Scenario 3

Glacier and Snow Runoff

Scenario 3 is applied in the Marsyangdi river basin only as Chepe Khola catchment has no glacial covered area. In this scenario, all glacier-covered area below 5,428 masl is converted into bare land. On shifting glacial covered area by 1,500 masl than the current altitude (3,928), the glacial covered area gets decreased by 3.2 % only and thus the bare area increased by the same (table 9).

Table 9 Change in the glacial covered area in scenario 3

Area in percentage		
Description	Baseline	Scenario 3
Bare Areas	18.9	22.1
Glaciers	13.3	10.1

Only a 3.2% decrease in glacial-covered area causes an average decrement of 10% in river discharge in year-round than the baseline. The discharge has been decreased by 21% (sharp) in April and by 4% (least) in January (figure 30).

Figure 30 Discharge on the scenario of changing the glacial area in MRB

Summary of Impact of Different LULC Scenarios

The simulated discharge increased by 1 % in scenario 1 in the Marsyangdi river basin and Chepe Khola catchment but runoff components have shown opposite behaviors among them. In scenario 2, overall discharge is increased by 1% (table 10) in MRB and

by 2% CKC (table 11). Evapotranspiration is decreased by 2% in scenario 1 in both (MRB and CKC) but in scenario 2, evapotranspiration is decreased by 4 in the Marsyangdi river basin (table 10) and by 6% in Chepe Khola catchment (table 11).

Table 10 Impacts of different scenarios in the Marsyangdi river basin

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
	Change in percentage		
Surface Flow (RD1)	+10	+1	-
Interflow (RD2+RG1)	-13	+1	-
Base flow (RG2)	-11	+3	
Simulated Discharge	+1	+1	-10
Actual Evapotranspiration	-2	-4	-

Table 11 Scenarios in Chepe Khola catchment

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
	Change in percentage	
Surface Flow (RD1)	-12	-0.3
Interflow (RD2+RG1)	+25	+4
Base flow (RG2)	+11	+6
Simulated Discharge	+1	+2
Actual Evapotranspiration	-2	-6

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5.1 Basin and Catchment Hydrology

Hydrological research improves the understanding of hydrologic processes, the role of hydrological systems in providing water for ecosystems and society, and of the water cycle in the functioning of the earth system (Koch & Weltzien, 2018). Marsyangdi river is one of the significant rivers for Nepal in many prospective such as hydropower, irrigation, ecosystem need, etc. Marsyangdi river contributes 16% in March and 15% in August, of the total flow in Narayni river at Devghat station, considering 4,634 m³/sec as discharge in Narayani river from the study of Panthi et al. (2015). Chepe Khola contributes 12% of average discharge to Marsyangdi river.

5.1.1 Model Calibration and Validation

Calibration and validation are an inevitable step prior to any model application (Mohammad et al., 2018). Most time direct solvation method cannot be used and parameters have to be determined by "trial and error" processes (Krause & Kralisch, 2005). Hit and trial method was used to calibrate the model in the Marsyangdi river and in Chepe Khola catchment.

The J2000 hydrological model was first calibrated in the Marsyangdi river basin with a hit and trial method for the period of 8 years from 2002 to 2009. The efficiencies have shown that the model can well represent the hydrological dynamics of the river basin. The model was then calibrated in the smaller catchment of Chepe Khola and found that the catchment dynamics were well represented by the model. The efficiencies in validation and overall period are greater than efficiency in calibration in Chepe Khola catchment and the efficiencies are almost similar in calibration period and overall period but lower in validation period in the Marsyangdi river basin. This may be because of data quality and period considered for calibration and validation. Any inconsistency in data for the period of 8 years in calibration may have resulted the lower efficiency. The data quality of recent years may have been consistent and improved.

5.1.2 Water Balance Components

The Marsyangdi river basin receives input in the form of precipitation (rainfall and snowfall), ice melt and snowmelt. The received water leaves the basin by

evapotranspiration and river discharge or is stored in the form of snow/ice, soil water, deep storage.

The Marsyangdi river basin receives precipitation in the form of rain (80%) and snow (20%). The total rainfall is way more than snow falls in the basin. The precipitation is higher in the areas of altitude between 800-1200 masl (lower part of MRB), but very low in areas with higher elevation (upper parts of the basin) in Manang district. The region is also known as the rain shadow region of Nepal. The daily precipitation between 1987 to 2015 have shown slightly decreasing trend. Prajuli et al (2016), predicted a decrease in rainy days while an increase in the frequency of intense rainfall, increase in rainfall for 2050's scenario. Only the stations inside the boundary of the river basin is considered in this study whereas some studies in the past also have considered nearby stations like Gorkha, Lake Samdo, Bandipur and result is somewhat different.

Out of total water received, 79% drains out of the basin as river discharge. This is aligned with the water balance of many other river basins in Nepal. In the Koshi River basin, 72% of total input flows out of the basin as discharge (Nepal, 2012) and in the Karnali basin, 66% of total input flows out of the river basin as discharge (Khatiwada & Nepal, 2016). The overland flow contributes most on the river discharge than interflow and base flow. Since the discharge is highly dominated by rainfall, overland flow is naturally the highest. The river discharge in MRB is contributed significantly (by 30%) by snow/ice melt. The basin whose glacier fraction is less than 5% can provide a significant contribution from ice melt to summer runoff when water is most needed for irrigation (Sorg et al., 2012). Since the glacier-covered area is 13.3% in MRB and the water from snow and ice melt is significant to summer runoff.

About one-fifth of total water received leaves as evapotranspiration. The key controls on evapotranspiration are rainfall interception, net radiation, advection, turbulent transport, leaf area, and plant-available water capacity (Zhang et al., 2001). In pre-monsoon season (April, May and early June), the potential evapotranspiration is higher than actual evapotranspiration but in other seasons, actual and potential evapotranspiration are all most equal. The water availability in the basin in pre-monsoon is decreased because of higher temperatures, lengthy sunshine hour and higher wind-speed than in another season. The seasonal trend (Lambert & Chitrakar, 1989) of evapotranspiration is similar like in other basins in Nepal. Evapotranspiration is higher in low altitudes and river

corridor (figure 14). This may be due to forest coverage and intense agriculture in the lowlands. Potential evapotranspiration measures the ability of the atmosphere to remove water from the surface, whereas actual evapotranspiration is the quantity of water that is actually removed from a surface due to the processes of evaporation and transpiration. So, the potential evapotranspiration is always higher than the actual evapotranspiration. The difference between actual and potential evapotranspiration is higher in the months of April, May, and June.

In the Marsyangdi river basin, out of total input received, 5.5% is stored in different forms. The storage includes interception storage, snow storage out of the glaciated area, glacier storage (snow above glacier and ice), medium and large pore storage, interflow storage, deep percolation storage, and channel storage. In MRB, snow over glacier stores highest amount followed by snow in the non-glacial area. In Chepe Khola catchment, very less amount of water (0.01%) is stored and most of the water is stored in the interflow 2 region. Unlike in MRB, almost no water is stored in the form of snow and ice in the catchment.

5.2 Scale Factor in Hydrology

The area of Marsyangdi river basin (4,074 sq. km) is 13 times of the area and Chepe Khola catchment (307 sq.km). Similarity principle has been used in different studies, such as runoff production, rainstorm intensity, and variability, soil characteristics, etc. Similarity theory is well considered in the field related to hydrology (e.g. hydrodynamics and turbulence) but limited research has been conducted in land-surface modeling and hydrology itself (Sposito, 2008). Scaling in hydrology is more advanced than the similarity principle.

In MRB, most of the water received (75%) leaves as discharge, one fifth (20%) as evapotranspiration and the remaining one twentieth (5%) is stored in different forms. The storage in Chepe Khola catchment is very less (<1%). This may be because the catchment has no glacial covered area and its location in the region with high evapotranspiration. The difference in potential and actual evapotranspiration is less in small catchment than the difference in the basin.

In scenarios of forest clearance and altitudinal swapping of forest and cultivated land, the overall discharge and evapotranspiration followed a similar pattern in the larger basin and smaller catchment. The runoff was increased due to the impact of clearing forest

vegetation Comet catchment (Siriwardena et al., 2006) and similar in small Brigalow catchment. Unlike in this research, the study of Siriwardena et al. (2006) developed models to estimate the impact of land cover changes in small catchment experiments and supposed to be applicable at a large scale.

Although the overall runoff remains almost the same, the contribution of the single components was changed significantly. The surface runoff is increased but interflow and base flow are decreased in the Marsyangdi river basin. This is similar to the behavior shown by Mulde catchment (Krause, 2002). But, the small Chepe Khola catchment shows the opposite behavior. The surface runoff was decreased but interflow and base flow were increased in both scenarios. Also, the monthly variation is higher in different scenarios.

5.3 Impact of Land Use Land Cover Change (LULC)

Improved understanding of hydrologic responses to LULC changes and provide needed knowledge for the management of land use and integrated water resource. Surface runoff and actual evapotranspiration (AET) were selected as important hydrologic elements to indicate the hydrologic response to LULC changes (Fang et al., 2013). Alike in the study of Fang et al (2013), evapotranspiration and three different runoff components are analyzed to understand the impact of LULC in the Marsyangdi river basin and the Chepe Khola catchment. The three different scenarios have a distinct and significant impact on the evapotranspiration, discharge and runoff components.

5.3.1 Impacts on Evapotranspiration

The actual evapotranspiration is decreased in both the Marsyangdi river basin and in Chepe Khola catchment in scenario 1 and in scenario 2. The impact of LULC change is less influential in the non-flood season and more influential in flood season (Fang et al., 2013) and is similar in MRB. The decrement in scenario 1 is the same but decrement in scenario 2 is higher in Chepe Khola. As Chepe Khola lies in the area in which the evapotranspiration and precipitation are higher than other areas in MRB, the evapotranspiration is significantly changed with the change in vegetation (cropland, forest type etc.). The differences evapotranspiration in MRB and CKC may have arisen due to the spatial distribution of soil water storage capacity and temporal rainfall as of study of Zhang et al. (2001).

5.3.2 Impacts on Runoff Components

Simulated discharge is increased (by 1%) in both Marsyangdi river basin and Chepe Khola catchment when all forest is cleared as imagined in scenario 1. The runoff is increased by 2% in the Koshi river basin when the forest is changed into agricultural land (Sharma et al., 2000). When the cropland area is changed in scenario 2, the impact is more in small catchment than in bigger basin. But, in the opposite, when the tropical moist forest throughout the Amazon Basin and South East (SE) Asia has been replaced by scrub grassland (Henderson & Sellers et al., 1993) reported large (30%) runoff decreases and a larger difference between the changes in evaporation and precipitation. As imagined in scenario 2 in MRB, when the agricultural land use of Tocantins River, Southeastern Amazonia, increased with no significant change in precipitation, annual mean discharge increased by 24% (Costa et al., 2003). The result is also consistent with the idea that states, the higher the total vegetation cover, the less the amount of runoff is (Thakur et al., 2017). In small catchment like Chepe Khola, the role of specific forest type is detectable. The hypothesis in scenario 2 is also near to reality. In Lamjung district, an increase in forest cover (above 1400 masl) has been observed with a consequent decrease in agricultural land and shrubland (grassland) but at lower elevations (below 1400 m), agricultural land area has increased (KC et al., 2017). Oppositely, surface runoff always decreased as the LULC scenarios changed from 1976 to 2007 during all periods, following the LULC changes with less influence on surface runoff in non-flood seasons, but similar to MRB, more influence in flood seasons, especially in July, August, and September, when the crops grow best (Fang et al., 2013).

The overland flow (RD1) is decreased (by 12%) in Chepe Khola catchment but increased (by 10%) in the Marsyangdi river basin in scenario 1, when the forest is cleared. The rainfall immediately contributes to flow as there is no tree for interception and also has very little infiltration in the absence of forest. This result is produced by changing SoilMaxT80 parameters in the model to control the infiltration. The chances of flood increases followed by a high level of erosion when the forest is cleared. In scenario 2, there is a slight increment in overland flow in MRB but is almost the same in Chepe Khola.

Inter flow (RD2+RG1) is decreased (by 13%) in MRB but increased (by 12%) in Chepe Khola in scenario 1. As the infiltration decreases with the clearance of forest, the contribution as interflow also decreased. In scenario 2, when the area of cropland is

changed, interflow is increased in MRB and Chepe Khola. The cropland and area of forest have a different role in the whole basin and in a small catchment. The small catchment is dominated by forest and cropland but there is every kind of landforms in MRB.

Base flow is decreased in the Marsyangdi river basin but increased in Chepe Khola catchment in scenario 1 and increased in the same fashion for both in scenario 2. The forest cover influences infiltration, soil moisture, and root system and hence influence water mobility. This may be the reason behind the different behavior in scenario 1 and scenario 2.

5.3.2 Impacts of Decrement in Glacial Covered Area

The small changes in the glacial area (decreased by 3%) can have a very large impact in overall river discharge (decreased by 10%) in the glacial fed river like the Marsyangdi river. This result is similar to the scenario from Zailiyskiy Alatau, in which the glacial runoff has decreased, thus the overall discharge in the river (Sorg et al., 2012). The glacial area in the Gandaki river basin as a whole is reported to be decreasing (Panthi et al., 2015). In hotter months (March, April, May), the contribution of snow and glacier melt is even higher than in other months and the impact of the reduction in area is more prevalent in this season. Reduction in glacial area and impact on runoff may cause a serious impact on hydropower generation, irrigation, and water sharing among different sectors.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 Conclusion

The J2000 hydrological model is able to represent hydrological dynamics for the period of 1987-2015 in the Marsyangdi river basin and the Chepe Khola catchment. The model is able to represent peak flows and dry season flows in the basin and the catchment. The J2000 hydrological model is very useful for understanding water balance and analysis of all water balance components of the river basin and its smaller catchment.

The scale factor in the hydrology of MRB is very important. The river basin and its small catchment do have different hydrological characteristics and also behave differently in different scenarios of land use land cover change. The evapotranspiration, overall discharge, overland flow, interflow, and base flow varies differently in different scenarios. Small perturbation (like change in LAI, shifting of agricultural land) in small catchment (for instance, Chepe Khola catchment) shows significant change in evapotranspiration and runoff components (overland-, inter- and base- flow) but in larger river basin (for instance, Marsyangdi river basin), the impact on overall river hydrology is very difficult to trace in basin scale. This iterates that, the effect of LULC is distinctly observed in the hydrology of the small catchments and thus suggests for considering the smaller catchments in the policy level and developmental activities and other similar studies. Therefore, it is of great importance to consider the heterogeneity of small catchment, its role in the downstream, and integrated management of the basin.

As average yearly snow/glacier contribution is 30% in the Marsyangdi river basin, even very little reduction in the glacial covered area in higher Himalayas may bring the serious concern of water availability in downstream, as discharge decrease significantly with the reduction. In April and May, overall discharge in the river reduces significantly upon the reduction in the glacial covered area. This may result in significant impact on hydropower generation and irrigation in the basin as the basin is recognized for caskets of hydropower plants and monsoon crops.

6.2 Recommendation

For Researchers,

- to capacitate with excellent skills on data analysis and modeling in data deficit areas

- to conduct a detailed study on the hydro-geology, soil and other physical characters in the basin
- to conduct microscale studies in the Himalayan basins since the nature of small catchment and larger basin may not be exactly the same.

For policy and infrastructural projects

- to conduct a detailed study in land use change and water availability in different scenarios before planning projects (e.g. hydropower, irrigation (small or large), dam, water supply, etc.) in order to have successful long-run of the projects
- to formulate and implement land use policy and project implementation policies prioritizing the watershed characteristics and hydrological dynamics of the basin

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

Detail description of Meteorological and hydrological data

Name	Description	Unit
ahum.dat	absolute humidity	g/cm ³
orun.dat	measured flow passage at the runoff	m ³ /s
rain.dat	measured amount of precipitation	mm
rhum.dat	relative humidity	%
sunh.dat	sunshine duration	h
tmax.dat	maximum temperature	°C
tmean.dat	mean air temperature	°C
tmin.dat	minimum temperature	°C
wind.dat	wind speed	m/s

APPENDIX 2

Detail description for soil parameter file

Parameter	Description
SID	soil type ID
depth	soil depth
kf_min	minimum permeability coefficient
depth_min	depth of the horizon above the horizon with the smallest permeability coefficient
kf_max	maximum permeability coefficient
cap_rise	Boolean variable, that allows (1) or restricts (0) capillary ascension
aircap	air capacity (equivalent to large pore storage (LPS))
fc_sum	usable field capacity (equivalent to middle pore storage (MPS))
fc_1 ...22	usable field capacity per decimeter of profile depth

APPENDIX 3

Details of Land Cover parameters

Parameter	Description
LID	land use ID
Albedo	Albedo in %
RSC0_1	minimum surface resistance for water-saturated soil in January
RSC0_12	minimum surface resistance for water-saturated soil in December
LAI_d1	leaf area index (LAI) at the beginning of the vegetation period (Jan-Mar)
LAI_d4	leaf area index (LAI) at the end of the vegetation period (Oct-Dec)
effHeight_d1	effective vegetation height at the beginning of the vegetation period (Jan-Mar)
effHeight_d4	effective vegetation height at the end of the vegetation period (Oct-Dec)
RootDepth	root depth
SealedGrade	sealed grade of surface

APPENDIX 4

Details of Hydrogeological parameters

Parameter	Description
ID	HRU ID
x	easting of the centroid point
y	northing of the centroid point
elevation	mean elevation
area	area
type	drainage type: HRU drains in HRU (2), HRU drains in channel part (3)
To_poly	ID of the underlying HRU
To_reach	ID of the adjacent channel part
slope	slope
aspect	aspect
Flowlength	flow length
SoilID	ID soil class
LanduseID	ID land use class

APPENDIX 5

Details of HRU parameters

Parameter	Description
ID	HRU ID
x	easting of the centroid point
y	northing of the centroid point
elevation	mean elevation
area	area
type	drainage type: HRU drains in HRU (2), HRU drains in channel part (3)
to_poly	ID of the underlying HRU
to_reach	ID of the adjacent channel part
slope	slope
aspect	aspect
Flowlength	flow length
SoilID	ID soil class
LanduseID	ID land use class

APPENDIX 6

Details of Reach parameters

Parameter	Description
ID	channel part ID
length	length
to-reach	ID of the underlying channel part
slope	slope
rough	roughness value according to MANNING
width	width

APPENDIX 7

Calibration Parameters

S.N	Module	Parameters	Description	Range	Value for Basin
1	Precipitation	Trans	threshold temperature	0 to - 5	0.9
2		Trs	base temperature for snow and rain	-5 to +5	-1
3	Interception	a_rain	interception storage for rain	0- 5	1.0
4		a_snow	interception storage for snow	0-5	1.2
5	Snow	baseTemp	Threshold temperature for snowmelt	-5 to +5	0.5
6		t_factor	Melt factor by sensible heat	0 to 5	3
7		r_factor	melt factor by liquid precipitation	0 to 5	5
8		g_factor	melt factor by soil heat flow	0 to 5	8
9		snowCritDens	critical density of Snow	0 to 1	0.4
10		snowColdContent	critical density of Snow	0 to 1	
11		ccf factor			0.012
12		snow_trs	Base temperature	-5 to 5	1
13	Melt Formula			2	
14	debrisFactor	debris factor for ice melt	0 to 10	3	
15	Glacier	tbase	Threshold temperature for snowmelt	-5 to +5	-1
16		meltFactorIce	Melt factor for ice melt	0 to 5	3.5
17		kIce	routing co-efficient for ice melt	0 to 50	8
18		kSnow	routing co-efficient for snowmelt	0 to 50	5
19		kRain	routing co-efficient for rain runoff	0 to 50	5
20		alphaIce	radiation melt factor for ice		0.2
21		ddfIce			6
22		soilMaxDPS (mm)	maximum depression storage	0 to 10	2
23	soilLinRed	linear reduction co-efficient for AET	-5 to 5	0.1	
24	Soil	soilMaxInfSummer (mm)	maximum infiltration in summer	0 to 200	70
25		soilMaxInfWinter (mm)	maximum infiltration in winter	0 to 200	85
26		soilMaxInfSnow (mm)	maximum infiltration in snow covered areas	0 to 200	60
27		soilImpGT80	infiltration for areas greater than 80% sealing	0 to 1	0.5
28		soilImpLT80	infiltration for areas lesser than 80% sealing	0 to 1	0.5

29		soilDistMPSLPS	MPS-LPS distribution coefficient	0 to 10	3
30		soilDiffMPSLPS	MPS-LPS diffusion coefficient	0 to 10	3
31		soilOutLPS	outflow coefficient for LPS	0 to 10	0.8
32		soilLatVertLPS	lateral vertical distribution coefficient	0 to 10	1.5
33		soilMaxPerc (mm)	maximum percolation rate to groundwater	0 to 100	22
34		soilConcRD1Flood	recession coefficient for flood event	0 to 10	1.2
35		soilConcRD1Flood threshold	threshold value for soilConcRD1Flood	0 to 500	300
36		soilConcRD1	recession coefficient for overland flow	0 to 10	2.6
37		soilConcRD2	recession coefficient for Interflow	0 to 10	3.5
38		gwRG1RG2dist	RG1-RG2 distribution coefficient (higher value increase proportion of input water to RG2 zone)	0 to 10	1.2
	Ground Water				
39		gwRG1Fact	adaptation for RG1 flow higher value will lead to less outflow and more water remains in them	0 to 10	1
40		gwRG2Fact		0 to 10	0.8
41		gwCapRise	capillary rise coefficient	0 to 10	0.02
		flowRouteTA	calibration parameter for adapting velocity of flow waves (higher value increases velocity of runoff waves and more water flows from channel)	0 to 10	7
42	Reach Routing				
43		Tmax.rate of Change			2
44	Scenarios	Tmeanrate of chnage			2
45		Tmin rate of change			2
46		increase/decrease in ppt			1.1